

INTELLIGIBLE GUI FOR MONITORING AND PROPAGATION OF BIOMEDICAL SIGNAL**Prabhjot Kaur¹, Lillie Dewan²**¹Research Scholar, ²Professor,^{1,2}Electrical Engineering Department,National Institute of Technology, Kurukshetra, Haryana, India

Abstract: Remote pregnancy monitoring has been gaining momentum in recent times. Observing maternal abdominal Electrocardiogram (ECG) signals throughout the gestation period is imperative to analyze complex cardiac diseases. Though vast research has been reported on the extraction of Fetal ECG signals from abdominal ECG signals using different techniques and algorithms, hardly any Graphical User Interface has been designed. The authors of the paper present an efficient and reliable Graphical User Interface to provide an automatic diagnosis of cardiac disorders with good accuracy and less computational complexity. It uses an Independent Component Analysis technique and hybrid filters to isolate and assess quantitatively Fetal and mother ECG signals. It offers a timely and appropriate remedy to the patient by facilitating communication with a doctor located distantly using Internet Protocol. The digital data transmission and 2D visualization of ECG waveform become more accessible with LabVIEW.

Keywords: Electrocardiography, Cardiac Disorders, Signal-To-Noise Ratio, Independent Component Analysis, Hybrid filters, LabVIEW, GUI, Video-Teleconference (VTC), patient care.

1 Introduction

Telemonitoring is a kind of healthcare that allows a patient to use a graphical user interface to perform a routine test and send the test data to a healthcare professional in real-time. Since the COVID-19 pandemic, the remote monitoring of expectant mothers has become the new norm to lessen the risk of virus transmission. The pregnant's are suggested to limit their exposure by avoiding in-person clinic visits as they are most vulnerable to infection. Besides, there is a dearth of healthcare personnel in remote areas and people have to travel long distances to consult a doctor. In such circumstances, there arises a need for some sort of unique telecare system that virtually monitors mothers' and fetuses' health during gestation. The proposed remote physiologic monitoring system involves advanced digital technologies and biomedical signal processing algorithms that would contribute to the prenatal care of pregnant women. These algorithms help mothers-to-be and their fetus to stay healthy during gestation and clinical diagnosis.

The analysis of cardiac diseases from ECG signals has great significance in medical applications. Obtaining a good quality Fetal Electrocardiography (FECG) signal from the Abdominal Electrocardiography (AECG) signal always remains challenging. Comprehending the morphology

of the Fetal ECG signal, even if successfully separated from the mother ECG signal, is still a rigorous task (Kaur and Dewan, 2021).

A Graphical User Interface (GUI) implemented by using Keras and Tensorflow in Python has been proposed (Gyohten et. al, 2020) using a convolutional neural network and long short-term memory method to detect arrhythmia automatically by modeling normal ECG signals. Another Graphical User Interface (Richards et al., 2020) developed using commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components decodes and plots the data received from wearable continuous electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring device. Data can be transmitted in both directions between device and computer by a data transceiver (TRx) via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connection. Murugappan et al., 2014 developed a GUI in LabVIEW software for monitoring and recording ECG signals and predicting sudden cardiac arrest (SCA). A wavelet-based hidden Markov model has been developed by (Sangaiah et al., 2020) for classifying cardiac arrhythmia into Normal (N), Right Bundle Branch Block (RBBB), Left Bundle Branch Block (LBBB), Premature Ventricular Contraction (PVC) and Atrial Premature Contraction (APC). An Android Smartphone-based FEKG monitoring system was proposed by (Yuan et al., 2019) that integrates a fast fixed-point independent component analysis algorithm (FastICA) and the sample entropy algorithm for the real-time extraction of fetal ECG signals from the maternal abdominal ECG signals.

The main objective of this research work is to design a Graphical User interface (GUI) for monitoring maternal Abdominal ECG (AECG) signals remotely during gestation and intended for critical analysis of complex cardiac diseases for both mother and fetal. Different signal processing techniques, improved algorithms, and enhanced methodologies have been implemented for monitoring and analysis of AECG signals. The GUI has been developed in a LabVIEW framework. The single biggest advantage of using LabVIEW is that it enables parallel processing i.e., multiple tasks can be performed at once and hence we can monitor the data during its acquisition. Also, its graphical programming environment is highly interactive and simple to use. Due to its graphic nature, the programs also known as virtual instruments (VIs) took less time to develop with the easy and quick transfer of the outcomes at the output level of display.

Although vast research has been made on the extraction of fetal ECG signals from abdominal ECG signals using different techniques and algorithms, seldom any GUI has been designed on this subject matter. Multiple functionalities, several standalone subVI's and the following utilities were incorporated into a user interface to make it more interactive:

1. Remote pregnancy monitoring (RPM) technology to develop a highly efficient and reliable LabVIEW-based GUI that involves proactive nursing of the Abdominal ECG of an expecting mother.
2. An algorithm that extracts FEKG signal from mother abdominal signal non-invasively with low computational complexity. The algorithm also concludes the cardiac disorders and arrhythmias and controls the same with medical intervention.
3. Information on fetus health during different phases of pregnancy.
4. A pathway to transmit the analyzed data from LabVIEW to the Google account of the doctor at a distant location to inform him regarding fetal and mother's health status.
5. Communication with the doctor through audio-visual mode if required.

6. Provision of google maps service to locate the nearest doctor's clinic at crucial times and the directions for the destination with minimum traffic.
7. Retrieval of medical records of the patient when required or the generation of the patient report on demand.

2. Methodology:

This paper attempts to present a methodology for evaluating and testing Graphical User Interface (GUI) on an artificial database in a LabVIEW environment. Multiple algorithms developed using LabVIEW to monitor mother and fetal health during gestation are integrated into a single Graphical User Interface to make the program more interactive.

The entire work involves three steps (Fig. 1):

- The acquisition of the biosignals (recorded fetal and maternal ECG signals) from an online databank.
- The processing, analysis, and visualization of the signal using the Virtual Instruments (VI's) which simulate physical equipment both in appearance and operation and then to arrive at a decision, the variation of the obtained signal values is compared with the online database values (FECGSYNDB) with an algorithm's help.
- The digital transmission of information to a doctor regarding the patient's wellbeing (mother and fetal).

The data source of recorded ECG signals and the GUI implementation has been discussed below.

Data Source

The Fetal ECG Synthetic Database (FECGSYNDB) taken from PhysioNet (Andreotti et al., 2016) consisted of simulated non-invasive fetal ECG signals. The database of 1750 realistic artificial signals have been generated using ten different pregnancies with seven different possible physical events as listed in Table 1 (Andreotti et al., 2016). Each simulation of 5 minutes in length has a resolution of 16-bit and 250 Hz sampling frequency. It was incorporated with five different additive noise levels (0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 dB) and has been repeated five times, totalling 145.8h of multichannel data and over one million fetal QRS complexes.

3. GUI Implementation

The Graphical User Interface, also known as the human-computer interface, acts as a means of interaction to monitor the mother and overall fetal health. The Flow chart of the execution of this GUI is presented in Fig. 2.

The front panel window of the GUI, illustrated in Fig. 3 offers seven virtual icons or controls whose functionality is connected to the VI palette in the block diagram. They are-

- | | |
|-------------------------|--|
| (a) Acquire Signal | (b) Acquire and Send Data in Real-Time |
| (c) Send Data Offline | (d) Get Patient Report |
| (e) Connect With Doctor | (f) Route Map |
| (g) Exit | |

The front panel of GUI exhibits four display tabs under the name Singleton Case, Twins Case, Health Status and Route Map. Singleton Case and Twins Case tab displays the waveforms of the respective analyzed signals (mother ECG signal with a single fetus and with double fetus respectively). The significant features extracted for diagnosing the abnormality and the nature of the abnormality diagnosed are shown under Health Status. The Route Map tab shows the destinations' available directions in a particular area. Another feature called Refresh Window allows the user to reset UI before acquiring the next data. Moreover, it ensures that the most currently acquired data is displayed. Additionally, GUI provides the exact date and time of patient data acquisition. The graphical source code is in the block diagram window of the GUI, where the algorithms designed for all the controls discussed in the above subsections have been integrated.

The sub-VIs or the algorithms integrated into the GUI have been discussed below in the subsequent section.

(a) **Acquire Signal:** This control when pressed, as exhibited in Fig.4, a pop-up box appears to permit the user to choose one of the bio-signals. The Select Bio-Signal control has a pull-down menu button, which selects ECG1 and ECG 2 (Abdominal ECG signal of a mother with single pregnancy and with twin gestation respectively). On the choice of the signals, a dialog box appears that asks for selection between ten different pregnancies with 7 different possible physical events, incorporated with five different additive noise levels (0, 3, 6, 9, and 12 dB). After selecting a particular noisy ECG signal from the dataset, the signal algorithm starts executing in a separate window and analyses the data for any abnormality. The examined ECG waveforms are then reflected on the front panel of the GUI. The acquired and analyzed data is then saved in a text file to consult a doctor later on.

The composite abdominal ECG signal was highly contaminated with noise ranging from high (SNR=00dB) to low (SNR=12dB). For suppressing or eliminating this noise, the authors have proposed hybrid filters in their previous work. The application of the Independent Component Analysis (ICA) technique to extract FECG signals and identification of different morphological and statistical features of both mother and fetal have also been discussed. Certain analytical information has been deciphered on the grounds of these extracted features, which helps in analyzing cardiac disorders or heart arrhythmias.

(b) **Acquire and Send Data in Real-Time:** This button, when pressed down, acquires and monitors the selected signal and shares the analyzed data with the registered webmail account of a doctor at a distant location for the medication (Fig.5). A wireless communication network (Wi-Fi) is used for transmitting data. Another dialog box will appear on selecting a particular signal, which asks for the recipient's name and email address. After filling in the required fields, press the Ok button.

(c) **Send Data Offline:** This control works like the previous control. The only difference is that, rather than sharing the patient health data in real-time mode, it helps send the already saved patient health record (stored in a .txt file during acquiring signal control) as an email. Also, this control does not allow the user to gather data again. As shown in Fig. 6, when this button is pressed, a pop-up window appears to ask for some details like the recipient's name and email address. In the carbon copy (CC) field, the user has to enter the recipient's email address who will receive the copy of the email. This fill-up has been made optional. The mail body contains the message to a doctor and it

may also include the signature of the sender. The attachment field has a "choose file" button, which, when pressed, displays a dialog box that aids the user to select the file, which has to be sent as an attachment to the recipient. Once all the required fields get filled press the ok button to proceed further.

(d) **Get Report:** Get report control button enables the user to retrieve the patient records stored at a particular location on a computer. Print out of the saved report/data can be produced on demand.

(e) **Connect with Doctor:** A virtual meeting with a doctor could be arranged over the internet using integrated audio and video calls, and text messages regardless of their location. It helps the patient to share her report and interact with the Doctor in real-time without being physically located together. One of the Video-Teleconference (VTC) software, Microsoft's Skype, is used in this work for consulting a doctor virtually.

(f) **Route Map:** This control facilitates the user in locating a doctor within reach during a crucial time and providing the directions for the destination with the least traffic.

(g) **Exit:** The exit button, terminates the current session of the GUI and stops the GUI from performing any task.

4. Results and Discussions:

With the application of the ICA technique, the fetal ECG signal has been successfully separated from the AECG signals. Figure 7 demonstrates the analysis of the abdominal ECG signal of a subject with a single fetal examined under case 0 with noise level SNR00dB. The fetal ECG waveform segregated from the mother ECG signal is also exhibited along with extracted morphological features. On the grounds of extracted morphological and statistical features along with their heart rate values, certain cardiac abnormalities have been diagnosed. The classification of cardiac abnormalities in the case of a subject with a single fetal pregnancy is indicated in Fig.8.

The accuracy of the algorithm (extracting fetal ECG signals from complex abdominal signals) incorporated in the proposed GUI, is tested by comparing a number of observed values with the online database values (FECGSYNDB). Taking full benefit of the database (FECGSYNDB), a total of 1750 samples of synthetic ECG mixture signals have been considered. The data is acquired and their variation from database value is observed under different noise levels ranging from high noise (SNR 00dB) to low noise (SNR 12dB). This way we can say that the heart rate values observed by the medical personnel would be within the specified range of variation from the database value.

Our observations on the ten subjects with a single fetal show that the deviation of the acquired value considered across all the cases (0-4) and noise levels (SNR00dB - SNR12dB) is maximum as +3.55 and -3.51 in the case of fetal and is maximum of +2.86 and -3.05 for the maternal case. To generalize it, we can say that a maximum deviation of 4% (fetal) and 3% (mother) on either side would be on the safer side taking slight safety margins. Accordingly, the observer must be cautious if he observes a value of more than 153 bpm ($160 - 4\%$ of 160) approximately in the upper range and less than around 125 bpm ($120 + 4\%$ of 120) in the lower range in case of fetal and 97 bpm ($100 - 3\%$ of 100) in the upper range and 62 bpm ($60 + 3\%$ of 60) in the lower range in case of mother.

The competence of the suggested GUI has also been verified in the situation of twin pregnancy. A subject with twin fetals is examined under case 0 with SNR00dB and fetals (F1 and F2) extracted waveforms isolated from the AECG signal are visualized in Fig. 9 and detected cardiac anomalies are displayed in Fig. 10. The algorithm developed for the extraction purpose has been tested on ten subjects with twin fetals and findings reveal that the deviation of the acquired value considered across all the noise levels (SNR00dB - SNR12dB) is + 0.95 and - 0.97 maximum. In other words, a maximum 1% of deviation is observed in the case of twin pregnancy.

The fetal's health condition is considered normal if its heart rate lies between 120-160 bpm and for mothers the normal heart rate ranges between 60-100 bpm. If the heart rate falls below the normal value, the abnormality is known as sinus bradycardia and if it goes beyond the normal value, the disorder is termed as sinus tachycardia.

Table- 2 (a and b) represents the summarized content of the variation that occurs over every possible case (0 - 4) under SNR (00dB – 12dB) for a mother and a single fetal. Similarly, Table-2 (c) shows the deviation of values calculated in the case of twin pregnancy.

Figure 11 displays the successful retrieval of medical records on demand by pressing the Get Report Control button. To improve health or to take any action against illness an attempt is made to seek guidance or recommendations from a doctor or other healthcare professional by communicating with them virtually rather than face-to-face. In view of that, a Skype application (Fig.12) is called by LabVIEW for instant messaging, verbal/video chat, and video calls using an internet connection. Through this video-teleconference (VTC) software, live and interactive communication is possible. In case of emergency, a route planner (Fig.13) has been provided in the GUI which allows the patient to find directions to the destination with the least traffic and offers the facility to explore all available doctors located near them.

4. Conclusion:

An interactive and user-friendly LabVIEW-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been introduced which can be successfully used for acquiring, processing, monitoring, and analyzing vital anatomical ECG parameters of mother and fetal for automatic diagnosis of arrhythmias and other cardiac disorders. It facilitates:

1. Timely and appropriate remedy to the patient by facilitating the interaction with a doctor located distantly, using high-quality audio and video calls over Internet Protocol (IP) networks.
2. Enables the doctors or the healthcare professionals to analyze the subject's condition distantly, thereby reducing acute exacerbations that can land them in the emergency.
3. Besides saving costly antenatal visits, the developed mother- fetal health monitoring system also provides socio-economic benefits by reducing anxiety, infection risk, and other complications.
4. Ensures safe and healthy prenatal care which is a beneficial alternative to in-person consultations.
5. As LabVIEW has enough flexibility, the GUI can be upgraded anytime with more advanced features.

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FIGURES:

Figure 1: Project Methodology

Figure 2: Flow Chart of the Execution of GUI

Figure 3: Front Panel of GUI

Figure 4 : Control: Acquire Signal

Figure 5: Control: Acquire and Send Data

Figure 6: Control: Send Data Offline

Figure 7: ECG1 Signal Visualization

Figure 8: ECG1 Signal Health Analysis

Figure 9: ECG2 Signal Visualization

Figure 10: ECG2 Signal Health Analysis

Figure 11: Retrieved Patient Records

Figure 12: Video Calling with Doctor

Figure 13: Route Planner

TABLES:

Table-1: Different Physiological Events (Fernando Andreotti et al., 2016)

CASE	DESCRIPTION
Baseline	Abdominal Mixture (no noise or events)
0	Baseline (no events) + noise
1	Fetal Movement + noise
2	MHR/FHR Acceleration/Decelerations + noise
3	Uterine Contraction + noise
4	Ectopic Beats (for both fetus and mother) + noise
5	Additional NI-FECG (twin pregnancy) + noise

Table-2(a): Deviation of Estimated Maternal Heart Rate Values with respect to Standard Database Values (FECGSYNDB)

SUB (Heart Rate Value) *	Case	SNR 00dB		SNR 03dB		SNR 06dB		SNR 09dB		SNR 12dB	
		Estim-ated Value	Variatio-n (%)	Estim-ated Value	Varia-tion (%)						
Sub 1 (107.8) *	0	106.5	-1.21	105.8	-1.89	106.6	-1.09	108.3	0.42	106.8	-0.94
	1	107.4	-0.35	106.9	-0.81	107.0	-0.72	106.9	-0.82	108.1	0.26
	2	107.6	-0.23	105.1	-2.47	104.7	-2.91	105.6	-2.07	106.9	-0.80
	3	107.5	-0.32	105.8	-1.84	105.3	-2.33	110.5	2.53	109.9	1.94
	4	105.1	-2.51	106.8	-0.96	105.0	-2.62	104.7	-2.91	105.1	-2.48
Sub2 (105.2) *	0	104.1	-1.07	104.2	-0.95	105.7	0.45	104.9	-0.27	104.2	-0.92
	1	104.2	-0.95	105.4	0.17	104.2	-0.96	104.1	-1.06	105.5	0.28
	2	105.7	0.45	104.0	-1.19	103.2	-1.89	103.5	-1.58	104.0	-1.19

	3	104.9	-0.27	104.7	-0.47	105.7	0.47	104.0	-1.15	104.4	-0.81
	4	104.2	-0.92	104.9	-0.28	103.5	-1.61	104.1	-1.09	103.9	-1.25
Sub3 (77.3) *	0	78.3	1.25	76.7	-0.75	77.9	0.78	78.1	1.09	77.1	-0.27
	1	75.9	-1.80	75.4	-2.48	77.9	0.72	77.1	-0.31	76.8	-0.60
	2	75.8	-1.93	75.4	-2.46	79.1	2.33	76.5	-1.00	75.3	-2.57
	3	76.3	-1.27	78.5	1.59	77.5	0.19	77.5	0.19	76.8	-0.66
	4	75.5	-2.29	78.5	1.59	76.2	-1.37	76.7	-0.72	76.9	-0.58
Sub4 (68.5) *	0	68.0	-0.67	68.4	-0.22	67.9	-0.86	69.6	1.61	67.4	-1.61
	1	67.2	-1.84	68.8	0.39	68.0	-0.72	67.5	-1.47	67.9	-0.88
	2	66.5	-2.98	66.6	-2.77	68.3	-0.25	67.0	-2.23	66.6	-2.77
	3	67.3	-1.72	70.3	2.64	70.0	2.25	69.9	2.07	70.5	2.86
	4	66.6	-2.82	68.2	-0.47	66.6	-2.73	66.6	-2.82	68.0	-0.72
Sub5 (83.3) *	0	84.2	1.07	81.4	-2.29	82.5	-1.02	84.8	1.84	82.5	-1.02
	1	82.2	-1.27	82.9	-0.52	84.0	0.80	83.0	-0.31	82.1	-1.45
	2	85.7	2.85	82.6	-0.83	85.2	2.28	84.7	1.70	82.3	-1.22
	3	83.0	-0.32	81.4	-2.33	85.4	2.48	82.1	-1.42	81.5	-2.14
	4	81.1	-2.67	84.0	0.89	81.8	-1.85	83.0	-0.34	81.8	-1.76
Sub6 (97.8) *	0	98.1	-0.26	97.9	-0.11	98.1	-0.28	97.7	0.08	97.8	0.05
	1	97.7	0.07	97.9	-0.06	98.0	-0.25	97.4	0.41	97.6	0.21
	2	95.5	2.33	96.5	1.38	95.5	2.32	96.6	1.22	95.5	2.39
	3	99.5	-1.74	99.2	-1.40	98.7	-0.90	97.7	0.08	99.8	-2.08
	4	98.7	-0.96	95.5	2.39	97.3	0.53	98.1	-0.26	98.4	-0.59
Sub7 (52.1) *	0	52.8	-1.38	52.2	-0.12	51.3	1.48	53.1	-1.92	51.2	1.73
	1	51.4	1.36	52.9	-1.52	50.7	2.63	51.9	0.31	53.1	-1.88
	2	53.6	-2.82	52.1	0.04	52.0	0.12	53.2	-2.17	51.2	1.80
	3	52.5	-0.67	53.0	-1.73	52.6	-0.86	50.5	3.05	53.1	-1.82
	4	52.6	-0.86	52.8	-1.38	52.2	-0.17	52.8	-1.38	50.9	2.30
Sub8 (59.7) *	0	59.5	0.30	59.9	-0.30	58.2	2.51	60.3	-1.04	58.9	1.37
	1	60.1	-0.65	60.7	-1.68	58.0	2.78	60.7	-1.71	61.0	-2.21
	2	59.2	0.82	59.1	0.95	58.2	2.58	61.1	-2.33	59.0	1.26
	3	60.1	-0.64	60.4	-1.12	58.6	1.83	61.4	-2.76	60.2	-0.90
	4	59.1	1.07	59.1	1.07	58.5	2.01	60.2	-0.80	60.8	-1.83
Sub9 (88.0) *	0	88.1	-0.16	88.3	-0.28	88.0	-0.03	88.0	0.01	88.4	-0.44
	1	88.1	-0.12	88.0	0.02	88.2	-0.22	88.5	-0.53	87.2	0.90
	2	88.6	-0.73	86.2	2.08	88.3	-0.36	89.3	-1.50	87.4	0.64
	3	87.0	1.09	89.0	-1.16	87.5	0.61	89.5	-1.66	88.9	-1.02
	4	86.2	2.01	88.1	-0.11	87.2	0.90	87.2	0.90	88.6	-0.70
Sub10 (35.1) *	0	34.2	2.54	35.8	-1.99	35.7	-1.60	35.8	-1.99	36.0	-2.56
	1	34.4	1.99	34.7	1.08	35.8	-1.94	35.8	-1.94	35.9	-2.17
	2	35.8	-2.05	35.2	-0.23	34.2	2.56	34.6	1.48	35.0	0.26
	3	35.5	-1.03	35.6	-1.40	35.6	-1.51	35.9	-2.22	35.4	-0.74
	4	34.5	1.65	34.4	1.97	35.9	-2.19	34.0	3.05	35.6	-1.31

*Database (FECGSYNDB) Value

Table-2(b): Deviation of Estimated Fetal Heart Rate Values with respect to Standard Database Values (FECGSYNDB)

SUB (Heart Rate Value) *	Case	SNR 00dB		SNR 03dB		SNR 06dB		SNR 09dB		SNR 12dB	
		Estimated Value	Variation (%)								
Sub 1 (143.0) *	0	142.0	-0.69	144.1	0.75	143.9	0.64	143.3	0.22	143.6	0.40
	1	142.1	-0.65	142.4	-0.39	144.3	0.94	143.6	0.39	142.7	-0.24
	2	141.6	-1.01	139.6	-2.41	142.3	-0.48	144.8	1.29	147.7	3.29
	3	142.2	-0.57	144.0	0.70	145.2	1.56	140.0	-2.10	140.9	-1.50
	4	143.3	0.23	140.4	-1.83	143.3	0.22	142.2	-0.59	142.4	-0.40
Sub2 (120.6) *	0	120.2	-0.36	120.3	-0.27	121.0	0.33	119.8	-0.66	120.2	-0.30
	1	120.0	-0.46	120.4	-0.17	120.2	-0.32	120.8	0.14	120.8	0.16
	2	118.6	-1.67	118.3	-1.95	121.8	1.00	120.3	-0.25	122.8	1.82
	3	119.8	-0.66	117.9	-2.21	117.9	-2.21	123.2	2.11	118.3	-1.91
	4	121.4	0.64	120.4	-0.17	119.5	-0.91	121.0	0.33	119.1	-1.28
Sub3 (137.2) *	0	136.4	-0.56	136.8	-0.28	136.1	-0.83	139.2	1.42	137.6	0.32
	1	138.8	1.15	136.0	-0.85	137.0	-0.15	136.4	-0.57	137.4	0.17
	2	139.0	1.28	132.4	-3.51	135.3	-1.41	139.8	1.92	134.2	-2.16
	3	135.5	-1.25	135.7	-1.07	138.5	0.92	134.1	-2.24	137.6	0.30
	4	138.3	0.81	136.2	-0.72	135.5	-1.28	137.7	0.33	137.0	-0.15
Sub4 (112.9) *	0	112.0	-0.78	113.7	0.70	113.0	0.12	114.2	1.12	110.7	-1.92
	1	112.1	-0.72	112.0	-0.76	112.1	-0.75	113.0	0.12	113.3	0.31
	2	108.9	-3.51	115.7	2.47	110.7	-1.98	111.5	-1.26	110.2	-2.37
	3	111.7	-1.04	114.6	1.51	112.6	-0.29	116.9	3.55	112.6	-0.29
	4	112.1	-0.74	113.7	0.67	111.1	-1.59	113.1	0.19	112.0	-0.79
Sub5 (93.5) *	0	92.1	-1.52	93.6	0.13	93.6	0.06	93.7	0.25	93.1	-0.44
	1	93.6	0.14	93.2	-0.35	93.6	0.10	93.7	0.18	93.3	-0.25
	2	95.9	2.61	95.4	2.01	91.8	-1.86	90.7	-3.02	90.3	-3.47
	3	93.0	-0.56	93.2	-0.35	93.2	-0.35	94.3	0.90	90.7	-3.05
	4	90.5	-3.17	93.1	-0.44	93.6	0.13	92.1	-1.45	94.1	0.62
Sub6 (113.8) *	0	114.1	-0.25	113.6	0.14	114.2	-0.39	114.7	-0.82	113.5	0.27
	1	113.5	0.27	114.4	-0.50	114.3	-0.46	113.0	0.68	113.0	0.69
	2	115.8	-1.75	112.8	0.91	112.6	1.06	114.1	-0.26	112.8	0.85
	3	113.6	0.14	111.9	1.64	114.7	-0.81	112.5	1.18	112.8	0.90
	4	112.0	1.61	113.7	0.09	111.8	1.74	114.1	-0.22	113.7	0.08
Sub7 (128.1) *	0	128.5	-0.29	128.0	0.08	128.0	0.04	128.4	-0.21	128.3	-0.17
	1	127.4	0.53	129.0	-0.68	128.9	-0.66	128.0	0.08	128.0	0.07
	2	130.0	-1.50	126.5	1.27	128.4	-0.20	125.6	1.95	128.8	-0.57
	3	126.4	1.34	128.4	-0.26	129.0	-0.71	130.0	-1.49	126.5	1.22

	4	128.5	-0.28	129.0	-0.67	127.0	0.86	128.0	0.08	126.8	0.99
Sub8 (115.6)) *	0	116.2	-0.52	114.9	0.56	116.5	-0.75	116.8	-1.01	116.2	-0.49
	1	114.4	1.01	116.3	-0.66	116.1	-0.44	115.4	0.15	114.5	0.95
	2	113.4	1.91	117.2	-1.39	115.9	-0.27	116.5	-0.79	114.7	0.79
	3	115.2	0.29	116.3	-0.59	114.3	1.14	116.1	-0.46	113.5	1.77
	4	115.5	0.11	117.5	-1.64	115.6	-0.05	115.4	0.15	114.8	0.66
Sub9 (160.1)) *	0	160.4	-0.20	160.7	-0.39	159.9	0.16	159.2	0.58	161.2	-0.67
	1	159.7	0.28	160.1	0.01	160.9	-0.49	159.9	0.16	160.5	-0.22
	2	158.4	1.06	158.9	0.78	158.5	1.02	158.5	1.02	158.4	1.04
	3	158.1	1.27	158.4	1.08	162.0	-1.21	162.4	-1.46	161.9	-1.15
	4	160.1	0.01	160.3	-0.14	160.6	-0.31	160.6	-0.31	160.1	-0.02
Sub10 (121.8)) *	0	122.0	-0.16	120.6	0.99	121.4	0.30	122.6	-0.67	120.8	0.80
	1	121.4	0.32	121.5	0.25	121.8	-0.03	120.9	0.72	121.8	0.03
	2	122.4	-0.52	123.9	-1.71	119.7	1.70	120.0	1.47	122.3	-0.44
	3	123.5	-1.36	122.2	-0.34	122.8	-0.81	122.0	-0.16	122.6	-0.62
	4	120.4	1.12	122.1	-0.23	121.0	0.67	122.1	-0.23	120.4	1.12

*Database (FECGSYNDB) Value

Table-2(c): Deviation of Estimated Twin Fetal Heart Rate Values with respect to Standard Database Values (FECGSYNDB)

		FETAL1			FETAL 2		
		Database Value (FECGSYNDB)	Estimated Value	Variation (%)	Database Value (FECGSYNDB)	Estimated Value	Variation (%)
SNR00 dB	Sub1	143.0	143.7	0.47	143.4	143.6	0.12
	Sub2	120.6	120.5	-0.05	158.9	158.4	-0.32
	Sub3	137.2	136.4	-0.55	156.0	155.5	-0.29
	Sub4	112.9	112.8	-0.06	167.9	168.2	0.21
	Sub5	93.5	92.6	-0.88	194.7	196.0	0.67
	Sub6	113.8	113.4	0.35	123.3	122.4	0.73
	Sub7	128.1	128.1	0.00	131.9	134.0	-1.59
	Sub8	115.6	115.8	-0.17	146.2	145.3	0.62
	Sub9	160.1	160.6	-0.31	162.4	162.4	0.00
	Sub10	121.8	120.8	0.82	149.3	149.7	-0.27
SNR03 dB	Sub1	143.0	142.7	-0.23	81.5	82.2	0.87
	Sub2	120.6	121.1	0.43	128.3	127.5	-0.64
	Sub3	137.2	136.5	-0.52	104.1	104.2	0.05
	Sub4	112.9	113.1	0.19	139.7	139.6	-0.13
	Sub5	93.5	94.1	0.62	188.7	189.9	0.63
	Sub6	113.8	113.1	0.62	183.3	183.1	0.11
	Sub7	128.1	128.8	-0.55	188.2	186.1	1.12
	Sub8	115.6	116.3	-0.61	125.4	125.5	-0.08

	Sub9	160.1	160.3	-0.12	154.8	153.5	0.84
	Sub10	121.8	121.1	0.57	131.2	129.3	1.45
SNR06 dB	Sub1	143.0	142.2	-0.54	157.0	156.8	-0.13
	Sub2	120.6	121.7	0.95	124.3	124.6	0.27
	Sub3	137.2	136.6	-0.39	123.0	122.8	-0.13
	Sub4	112.9	112.6	-0.27	102.7	102.6	-0.13
	Sub5	93.5	93.6	0.15	160.9	161.3	0.26
	Sub6	113.8	114.0	-0.18	148.2	148.1	0.07
	Sub7	128.1	125.4	2.11	152.0	151.4	0.39
	Sub8	115.6	116.1	-0.43	126.2	126.7	-0.40
	Sub9	160.1	160.4	-0.19	125.0	125.7	-0.56
	Sub10	121.8	121.8	0.00	145.4	145.7	-0.21
SNR09 dB	Sub1	143.0	144.1	0.75	162.0	161.2	-0.48
	Sub2	120.6	120.8	0.23	147.5	148.1	0.41
	Sub3	137.2	137.1	-0.06	73.9	74.1	0.19
	Sub4	112.9	113.1	0.19	161.0	161.3	0.20
	Sub5	93.5	94.3	0.86	133.7	134.2	0.41
	Sub6	113.8	113.3	0.44	163.7	163.1	0.37
	Sub7	128.1	128.0	0.08	103.7	103.1	0.58
	Sub8	115.6	115.2	0.35	114.9	113.6	1.13
	Sub9	160.1	159.6	0.31	125.9	125.8	0.08
	Sub10	121.8	121.3	0.41	152.5	151.4	0.72
SNR12 dB	Sub1	143.0	142.9	-0.09	161.5	161.8	0.17
	Sub2	120.6	120.3	-0.22	154.7	154.9	0.15
	Sub3	137.2	137.1	-0.07	118.9	119.5	0.44
	Sub4	112.9	113.0	0.11	221.5	220.5	-0.42
	Sub5	93.5	93.4	-0.03	84.2	83.7	-0.66
	Sub6	113.8	112.5	1.14	141.7	140.9	0.56
	Sub7	128.1	128.2	-0.08	133.9	133.0	0.67
	Sub8	115.6	116.6	-0.87	129.3	127.6	1.31
	Sub9	160.1	160.3	-0.12	113.0	112.5	0.44
	Sub10	121.8	121.4	0.33	116.7	116.0	0.60